

Author: Ya-Wen Yang

Memo: Civil Society Engagement

Summary II

D7.6. tasks 3,4,5, 6, 7 and 8

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19820381

Memo: Civil Society Engagement Summary

The Taiwan team of WP5 held two focus group sessions on 19 and 22 December 2025 at the Institutum Iurisprudentiae, Academia Sinica, to finalise the second phase of the fieldwork. Seven representatives from non-governmental organizations (NGOs), who had also participated in the first phase, joined the discussions. To ensure a diversity of advocacy perspectives, participants included experts in both general human rights advocacy and migrant-specific issues. The majority of participants had also taken part in workshops and events held on 7, 8 and 10 November in Taipei. They were therefore familiar with the HRJ project and well positioned to advise on the formulation of the final recommendations. The discussions revolved around three key themes.

First, participants explored strategies for broadening the audience of human rights advocacy: What strategies can help human rights advocacy reach beyond the echo chamber and foster wider societal engagement? What types of advocacy approaches are most effective, and what lessons can be drawn from successful cases?

Second, the groups examined the impact of domestic political pressures and international geopolitics—particularly the global rise of right-wing populism—on advocacy efforts. Does this global trend serve as a driving force or a constraint for civil society engagement?

Finally, the discussion turned to the effects of international networking and local collaboration among NGOs. What strategic or pivotal role does the European Union play in supporting civil society advocacy in Taiwan?

Q1. Human Rights Discourse and Advocacy Strategies

When asked how NGOs use human rights discourse to draw public attention to migrant worker issues, most participants agreed that they tend to avoid using human rights terminology directly. In Taiwan’s context, “human rights” is often considered as a Western or abstract concept, associated with elite discourse rather than practical concerns. Instead, organizations prefer to frame issues in humanitarian terms—such as cases involving severe illness, sexual assault, or end-of-life care—because “purely humanitarian” appeals tend to elicit public sympathy and face less backlash. Humanitarian framing feels softer and more neutral, even charitable, aligning better with local cultural values of kindness and good deeds. By contrast, invoking “human rights” may be perceived as accusatory or confrontational, which can alienate potential supporters.

Participants emphasized that effective advocacy often begins with issues that are concrete, relatable, and capable of resonating with the public’s everyday experiences. Simplifying the

message and anchoring it in tangible realities, they argued, can significantly increase public receptiveness and support. A notable example came from the fisheries sector. In earlier years, industry representatives perceived civil society advocates as adversaries—accusing them of “speaking for foreigners” and acting against national interests. However, when advocacy groups strategically reframed their campaign around ensuring Wi-Fi access for migrant fishermen, the dynamic changed entirely. The Fisheries Agency, industry broadcasters, and fishing associations soon began promoting the narrative that “*fishermen are happy because they have Wi-Fi.*” What had once been a space of confrontation transformed into one of cooperation.

For the NGOs, the Wi-Fi initiative served as more than a symbolic gesture of goodwill. It provided a practical foundation for communication, collective organizing, and the strengthening of union networks—thereby contributing to the broader realization of labor rights. At a theoretical level, this reframing also reflected a critical stance toward traditional human rights discourse. Some NGOs questioned the applicability of human rights language to labor advocacy, expressing concern over its perceived universalism, abstraction, individualism, and judicialization—tendencies that may distance rights from the collective struggles necessary for their realization. Instead, they underscored the importance of grassroots democracy and group-based mobilization as essential to advancing labor rights in practice. In this sense, effective advocacy is not achieved through abstract appeals to universality, but through grounded narratives that connect directly with local experience and collective agency.

Moreover, participants observed that human rights discourse and advocacy strategies in Taiwan frequently rely on framing the protection of migrant workers as aligned with the interests of the domestic population. As advocacy efforts are primarily directed toward the general public and policymakers, emphasizing the benefits to Taiwanese society was described as a pragmatic approach for securing broader support and increasing the likelihood of policy uptake. Public health measures during the COVID-19 pandemic were cited as a key example of this framing strategy. Participants noted that non-governmental organizations promoted the bilingualization of government documents and the establishment of digital complaint and rights-notification mechanisms for migrant workers. These initiatives were presented not solely as measures to protect migrant workers’ rights, but as essential tools for strengthening overall pandemic control by reducing information asymmetries and preventing the spread of the virus, thereby safeguarding the health and safety of the wider population. Such framing was regarded as instrumental in persuading government authorities to enhance protections for migrant workers. By reducing migrant workers’ dependence on employers and brokers, these ostensibly technical reforms were seen as challenging the structural conditions that sustain the intermediary-based labor system. Participants further noted that these incremental changes align with advocacy organizations’ longer-term objective of dismantling the brokerage regime.

The final advocacy strategy discussed was “linking migrant issues to broader domestic concerns.” By embedding migrant worker issues within larger, locally resonant topics, advocates can avoid focusing too narrowly on migrant identity, which might otherwise create a sense of detachment or indifference among the general public. For example, in cases involving sexual assault of domestic migrant workers, participants shared that their organizations co-hosted press conferences with other NGOs—such as the Judicial Reform Foundation and the Garden of Hope Foundation—to call for stronger protections and greater accountability from both the government and private employers. By framing these incidents within the broader context of sexual violence prevention, rather than highlighting the victims’ migrant status, advocates found it easier to generate public empathy and engagement, ultimately making their campaigns more effective.

In sum, participants identified three effective advocacy strategies:

1. Use humanitarian rather than human rights language to evoke empathy and avoid ideological backlash.
2. Highlight mutual benefits, emphasizing that protecting migrants also safeguards Taiwanese society.
3. Integrate migrant issues into broader domestic debates, enhancing relatability and public support.

All three strategies share the goal of building familiarity and reducing social distance between migrants and the local public to make advocacy more effective.

Q2. Domestic Pressures and Geopolitical Context

Under the combined influence of domestic political pressures and geopolitical dynamics, advocacy for migrant workers’ rights in Taiwan generally faces a strong headwind. Among these factors, domestic pressures exert a greater impact than geopolitics, though the two are closely intertwined—geopolitical developments often intensify domestic constraints. In particular, when issues are framed through the lens of national security, migrant workers’ rights tend to become even more marginalized. As national security concerns increasingly shape policy decisions, their effects extend to migration-related matters. The legal and social status of spouses from China, for example, has become particularly difficult to advance, as it is frequently entangled with security-related sensitivities in Taiwan policymaking context.

Globally, the rise of right-wing populism—illustrated by movements such as Germany’s AfD, the Trump administration in the United States, and France’s National Rally—has fostered a more inward-looking political climate. This shift has influenced both the EU’s approach to refugee protection and Taiwan’s domestic discourse. In Taiwan, employer associations have echoed anti-immigration rhetoric reminiscent of the Trump era, using it to legitimize opposition to migrant labor reforms.

Domestically, Taiwan's political landscape further complicates advocacy efforts. Rising tensions with China and the institutional fragility of the current minority government under Lai Ching-te have heightened internal political pressure. As a result, legislators are often preoccupied with political gridlock, leaving limited bandwidth for issues perceived as peripheral, such as migrant labor rights. In contrast to earlier administrations, when NGOs could more easily engage with legislators and advance specific policy proposals, today's fragmented political environment has made such collaboration increasingly difficult. Consequently, domestic political pressures—amplified by geopolitical anxieties—have deepened the marginalization of migrant worker issues and hindered progress in rights advocacy.

Moreover, the fundamental reason why policies concerning migrants face headwinds is that migrants lack voting rights. As foreigners do not possess voting rights, migrant issues attract limited attention from major parties and are not treated as priority matters.

However, geopolitics may also exert positive influence. Substantive progress on numerous human rights issues has been driven by external pressure from third countries and international NGOs. Example includes: First, the passage of the Uyghur Forced Labor Prevention Act (UFLPA) in the United States in 2021. The Act prohibits the importation into the United States of goods mined, produced, or manufactured wholly or in part in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region in China when implicated in forced labor. Second, reforms in Taiwan's distant-water fisheries, which NGOs emphasized were largely propelled by external pressure. Severe human rights concerns have long existed in Taiwan's distant-water fisheries, including excessive working hours, abusive working and living conditions, and lack of access to communication (Wi-Fi). Since 2015, the United States and the European Union have placed Taiwan on watch lists of illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU) due to forced labor concerns, prompting Taiwanese legislators to enact the *Act for Distant Water Fisheries* in 2016. In 2022, the Fisheries Agency—formerly oriented toward employer interests—introduced the *Action Plan for Fisheries and Human Rights* to improve migrant workers' rights and align with U.S. standards. Beyond the distant-water fisheries sector, the human rights conditions of migrant workers in industries such as electronics, textiles, manufacturing, and healthcare have also been gradually improving. Third, the 2025 Withhold Release Order (WRO) issued by U.S. Customs and Border Protection against Taiwan's bicycle manufacturer Giant, requiring remediation of migrant workers' rights violations such as excessive recruitment fees resulting in debt bondage. Giant has petitioned for the lifting of the WRO and submitted a corrective action plan. The Taiwanese government is also preparing revisions to its *National Action Plan on Business and Human Rights* and drafting forced labor guidelines.

Taken together, these examples show that pressure from third countries and international NGOs has been a key motivator for both the Taiwanese government and private sector to improve

migrant workers' rights. Notable outcomes include prohibitions on forced labor and reductions or elimination of excessive recruitment fees.

Industrial competition among states can likewise generate positive human rights impacts. Given the competitive relationship among Taiwan, Japan, and South Korea in industrial development, Taiwanese NGOs invoked recent advances in migrant worker rights in Japan and South Korea—such as Japan's 2022 *Guidelines on Respecting Human Rights in Responsible Supply Chains*—to press the Taiwanese government to follow suit. NGOs utilize the business and human rights framework and have established a cross-organizational coalition, Taiwan Transnational Corporations Watch (TTNC), to monitor related issues. In summary, inter-state industrial competition may similarly contribute to improvements in the human rights protections of migrant workers.

The reason geopolitics can generate positive human rights impacts in Taiwan is largely due to Taiwan's distinctive international status and the government's emphasis on human rights diplomacy. NGOs note that the Taiwanese government has long sought to construct its international image as a "beacon of democracy." Consequently, compared with domestic political pressure, the government tends to take international pressure more seriously and deploys human rights discourse as diplomatic rhetoric. Within this logic—where Taiwan distinguishes itself from China on the basis of human rights—human rights become a discursive tool through which NGOs can exert pressure on the government. However, absent external pressure, the extent to which the Taiwanese government voluntarily improves human rights of migrant workers remains limited.

Finally, we suggest that the EU can leverage external pressure and inter-state industrial competition to generate positive competition in the protection of migrant workers' rights. As illustrated in the preceding cases, the EU, as one of Taiwan's most significant trading partners, possesses considerable influence over Taiwan's policies. The EU may, through trade-related measures directed at the Taiwanese government, or by elevating scrutiny of migrant workers' rights across East Asian countries and thereby shaping inter-state industrial competition, directly or indirectly incentivize improvements in Taiwan's treatment of migrant workers.

Q3. International Networking and the Role of EU

NGOs observe that the EU can play two distinct roles in advancing the rights of migrant workers in Taiwan: that of an external source of pressure and that of a cooperative partner.

With respect to the EU's role as an external pressure, NGOs invoked the Chinese proverb "When it comes to business, we talk business", noting that the EU, as one of Taiwan's most significant trading partners, is uniquely positioned to use trade leverage or sanctions to

incentivize improvements in Taiwan’s treatment of migrant workers. NGOs emphasized that the EU plays a particularly critical role in the field of business and human rights, and that EU pressure can exert substantial influence on the Taiwanese government—indeed, even creating psychological pressure on certain officials—as illustrated by the EU’s warning issued to Taiwan’s distant-water fisheries. In other words, the EU is capable of functioning as a meaningful external source of leverage. With respect to forced labor, for example, NGOs noted that the EU may utilize its own Forced Labour Regulation to urge the Taiwanese government to relax its overly restrictive standards for identifying forced labor. More broadly, they argued that the EU should formally link human rights to trade, employing concrete punitive measures to promote compliance. For instance, if the Taiwanese government fails to improve the rights of migrant workers, or if Taiwanese companies are found to have products implicated in forced labor or other human-rights violations, the EU could suspend Taiwan’s visa-waiver privileges as a sanction.

With respect to the EU’s second role as a partner for cooperation, NGOs expressed the view that the EU could adopt a more proactive stance on migrant-worker rights and that its engagement with NGOs should be bidirectional. For instance, the EU convenes annual Taiwan–EU Human Rights Consultations to facilitate exchanges with the Taiwanese government and NGOs on human-rights issues. However, when EU representatives in Taiwan gather information through local NGOs, such engagement should not take the form of a one-way exchange of information. Rather, the EU should share its analyses, assessments, and anticipated follow-up actions with local NGOs. NGOs noted that despite investing substantial time and effort to share local realities to the EU during these activities, they often remain unaware of the EU’s concrete positions or likely responses on the issues discussed. Some NGOs even perceived these activities as resembling “labor education” sessions aimed at foreigners unfamiliar with Taiwan’s realities, which has understandably discouraged further engagement. Such inadvertent distancing could be avoided.

In our view, the EU can mitigate this problem by providing NGOs with more substantive feedback, recommendations, and even opportunities for cooperation—thereby fostering a genuinely reciprocal relationship. Additionally, NGOs suggested that individual EU member states could independently establish channels of engagement with Taiwan, such as reviewing whether bilateral trade involves goods implicated in forced labor, or providing financial support to strengthen the capacity and long-term development of Taiwanese NGOs.

The EU and the Taiwanese government may also pursue other forms of cooperation. First, the EU can provide human rights training programs for a wide range of Taiwanese public officials and NGOs. EU member states possess a deeper root of human rights culture, supported by extensive regulatory frameworks and implementation experience—capacities that Taiwanese officials generally lack. NGOs therefore suggested that the EU could introduce longer-term

training programs designed to more effectively internalize human rights concepts within Taiwan's administrative and legal systems. For example, the EU could participate in the training of Taiwanese judges and prosecutors, using case-based instruction to enhance protections for migrants. To address issues of racial profiling in policing, the EU could also provide human rights training to Taiwanese law enforcement personnel, with particular emphasis on senior officials who hold substantial policymaking authority. Second, with respect to refugee protection, NGOs noted that Taiwan currently lacks both a competent administrative authority and a comprehensive legal framework governing refugee affairs. Drawing on the experiences of its Asylum Agency, the EU could assist the Taiwanese government by supporting the establishment of a dedicated refugee protection authority and a corresponding legal regime.

In conclusion, with respect to international networking and the EU's role, NGOs expressed high expectations of the EU while also demonstrating a realistic understanding of its responsibilities and constraints. In relation to migrant rights issues, participants suggested that the EU make strategic use of its trade leverage. By insisting on effective implementation of trading partners' action plans on business and human rights, the EU could play a significant role in enhancing regional human rights performance and in setting leading standards. In addition, NGOs highlighted the EU's extensive experience in implementing human rights frameworks, which could be shared with local NGOs through training and capacity-building initiatives.

